

Multivariate fractional Brownian motion and generalizations of SABR model

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Abstract

The SABR model is a generalization of the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) model. It was introduced and analyzed by Hagan et al. (2002). Rapidly it has become the market standard for quoting cap and swaption volatilities thanks to the approximate formula for implied volatility which allowed real time risk management of large books of caps and swaptions. Later on it was also used in FX and equity markets.

The generalization introduces stochastic volatility to the CEV model. The volatility process is assumed to follow a geometric Brownian motion with zero drift, i.e., a martingale and no mean reversion. This assumption differs significantly from other models of stochastic volatility, where mean reversion is introduced.

In this paper another generalization of CEV and also of SABR is proposed. Namely, the Brownian motion defining the volatility process is replaced with a fractional Brownian motion. Such modification leads to the question of how one should define the dependence structure between the Brownian motion of the CEV model and the fractional Brownian motion of the new volatility process.

We link the choice to multivariate self-similarity property of stochastic drivers in the model.

1 Introduction

SARB model is defined by the following dynamics

$$\begin{aligned}dX_t &= X_t^\beta Y_t dW_t, X_0 = x, 0 \leq \beta \leq 1, \alpha \geq 0, \\dY_t &= \alpha Y_t dZ_t, Y_0 = \sigma, d\langle W, Z \rangle_t = \rho dt, |\rho| \leq 1,\end{aligned}$$

where the vector process (W, Z) is a bivariate Brownian motion with the correlation ρ .

Many properties of SABR depend on its parameters. For instance, SABR reduces to CEV when the volatility of the volatility is equal to zero, i.e., when $\alpha = 0$. Another important property is linked to the level of β . If $\beta < \frac{1}{2}$ the

process X hits 0 in finite time and the solution to the above equation may not be unique unless one specifies behavior at the boundary. For example, under the condition that when the process hits zero it stays there (it is absorbed at zero) the strong solution exists and is unique. Moreover, the strong solution exists and is unique when $\frac{1}{2} \leq \beta \leq 1$. The correlation ρ determines many properties of the above system. For instance, existence of moments of X , its uniform integrability, martingale versus local martingale property depend on it. Interested reader may consult P-L. Lyons, M.Musiela (2007) for details.

There have been many attempts in the past to introduce fractional Brownian motion into financial models. Most of them, however, replaced the Brownian motion driving the asset dynamics, namely our process X , with a fractional Brownian motion. However, fractional Brownian motion is not a semimartingale and hence the standard stochastic calculus methodology breaks down. In fact one can show that such model specification leads to an arbitrage in the classical sense, see Rogers (1997). In our generalization, however, we replace the Brownian motion Z with a fractional Brownian motion. One could argue that there is no difference and we would face the same difficulties. This is because one needs to give sense to the equation for Y and to the bracket process $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$. In this paper we address these issues.

We are not going to rely on the rough path theory to define the process Y . In our case there is no need to do it because the stochastic volatility of the SABR model can also be defined by the solution to the equation, namely, by

$$Y_t = \sigma \exp \left(\alpha Z_t - \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 t \right).$$

This representation suggests a more general class of models, with the stochastic volatility process given by

$$Y_t = \sigma \exp \left(\alpha Z_t - \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 \text{Var} Z_t \right),$$

where the continuous bivariate process (W, Z) is Gaussian with zero mean and W is a Brownian motion. Define the covariance function of (W, Z) by

$$\Sigma(s, t) = \begin{pmatrix} s \wedge t & K(s, t) \\ K(s, t) & L(s, t) \end{pmatrix},$$

where $K(s, t) = EW_s Z_t$ and $L(s, t) = EZ_s Z_t$

In order to define the bivariate Gaussian process (W, Z) one needs to choose the Gaussian process Z by choosing its covariance function $L(s, t)$ and to define the dependence structure between W and Z by choosing the function $K(s, t)$. The constraint is that the covariance function $\Sigma(s, t)$ is positive definite. The question is what arguments could be used to reduce the number of possible choices for the functions K and L .

2 Empirical evidence

What empirical evidence one could use to motivate the choice of K ?

Obviously, there will be an impact of the choice of the stochastic volatility process Y and of the dependence structure between the spot and its volatility on the movement of the spot. However, looking at the spot price movement alone may not be sufficient. The second source of information one could use is the joint evolution of the spot and of its stochastic volatility. The joint dynamics of X and Y determine the option prices.

We assume here that the option prices are quoted in terms of Black Scholes volatilities. It turns out that log-volatility behaves like a fractional Brownian motion with Hurst exponent H of the order 0.1 at any reasonable time scale, see Gatheral et al. (2018). Moreover, the at-the-money volatility skew is well approximated by a power function of time to expiry, see Bayer et al. (2016).

More precisely, if the implied Black Scholes volatility of an option as a function of log-moneyness k and time to expiration τ is denoted by

$$\sigma_{BS}(k, \tau)$$

the at-the-money (ATM) volatility skew is defined by

$$\psi(\tau) = \frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, \tau) |_{k=0}.$$

Empirical evidence suggests that for a large range of time to expiry

$$\psi(\tau) = C\tau^{-\alpha}, 0 < \alpha < \frac{1}{2}.$$

Moreover, Fukasawa (2017) shows that a model where log-volatility behaves like fractional Brownian Motion with Hurst exponent H generates ATM volatility skew of the form

$$\psi(\tau) = C\tau^{H-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

3 Fractional Brownian motion

When the process Z is a fractional Brownian motion with Hurst exponent H the volatility process Y defined in the introduction takes the form

$$Y_t = \sigma \exp\left(\alpha Z_t - \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2 t^{2H}\right).$$

Let us recall that a fractional Brownian motion is a continuous zero mean Gaussian process with covariance function given by

$$EZ_s Z_t = \frac{1}{2} \left(|s|^{2H} + |t|^{2H} - |t-s|^{2H} \right), s, t > 0, 0 < H < 1.$$

From now on we assume that the process Z is a fractional Brownian motion with Hurst exponent H .

In our model specification the process W is a Brownian motion and the process Z is a fractional Brownian Motion. The question remains how to specify the dependence structure between W and Z in order to define the bivariate Gaussian process (W, Z) . The covariance function of the bivariate process (W, Z) is given by

$$\Sigma(s, t) = \begin{pmatrix} s \wedge t & K(s, t) \\ K(s, t) & \frac{1}{2} \left(|s|^{2H} + |t|^{2H} - |t - s|^{2H} \right) \end{pmatrix},$$

where $K(s, t) = EW_s Z_t$.

In order to define the dependence structure it is enough to choose the function $K(s, t)$. The only constraint is that the covariance function is $\Sigma(s, t)$ is positive definite. This is a rather weak constraint and there are many possible choices one can make. For example, one can introduce another Brownian motion which is correlated with the one driving the asset dynamics and use it to define the process Z .

Indeed, it is well known that a fractional Brownian motion Z can be constructed with help of another Brownian motion, say, B . Interested reader can consult, for example, Jost (2006), for details.

We assume that the bivariate process (W, B) is a Brownian motion with correlation ρ or alternatively that $d\langle W, B \rangle_t = \rho dt$. One can define Z using B and Molchan-Golosov formula, namely,

$$Z_t = \int_0^t R(t, s) dB_s,$$

$$R(t, s) = c(H) F\left(\frac{1}{2} - H, H - \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} + H, \frac{s-t}{s}\right) (t-s)^{H-\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$c(H) = \sqrt{\frac{2H\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2} - H\right)}{\Gamma\left(H + \frac{1}{2}\right)\Gamma(2-2H)}},$$

where F is Gauss hypergeometric function and Γ is the gamma function. It is easy to see that

$$K(s, t) = EW_s Z_t = \rho \int_0^{s \wedge t} R(t, u) du,$$

where $\rho = EW_1 B_1$. Alternatively, one can define Z using Mandelbrot-Van Ness formula, where,

$$Z_t = \frac{1}{c_1(H)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R_1(t, u) dB_u,$$

$$R_1(t, u) = \left((t-u)^+\right)^{H-\frac{1}{2}} - \left((-u)^+\right)^{H-\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$c_1(H) = \left(\int_0^{\infty} \left((1+u)^{H-\frac{1}{2}} - u^{H-\frac{1}{2}}\right)^2 du + \frac{1}{2H}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

Note that for this construction we define the Brownian motion B on the real line. In this case we have

$$K(s, t) = EW_s Z_t = \frac{\rho}{c_1(H)(H + \frac{1}{2})} \begin{cases} t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} - (t-s)^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & 0 < s < t \\ t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & 0 < t < s \end{cases}.$$

Note that because the process (W, Z) can be viewed as a linear transformation of the process (W, B) , it is a bivariate Gaussian process and hence the matrix $\Sigma(s, t)$ is positive definite.

There are potentially other ways to define a fractional Brownian motion as a functional of the Brownian motion B each leading to a different specification of the dependence structure in the bivariate Gaussian process (W, Z) . Moreover, one can define the process (W, Z) without reference to another Brownian motion. The question remains what arguments one can use to motivate the choice.

4 Self-similarity

We are going to focus on the structural properties of the model that are desirable from the user perspective. Namely, on the self-similarity, and on the role it plays in financial modelling.

Perhaps the best example to use to explain the idea is to consider the classical Black Scholes model in which in order to derive the Black Scholes formula one simply calculates

$$E \left(\exp \left(\sigma W_T - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 T \right) - K \right)^+ = E \left(\exp \left(\sigma \sqrt{T} W_1 - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 T \right) - K \right)^+.$$

The above equality holds because the distributions of W_T and of $\sqrt{T}W_1$ coincide. This is obviously trivial from the mathematical perspective but important for the practitioners using such a model. Namely, the volatility parameter σ can be interpreted at different time scales. If σ represents the annual volatility, $T = 1$, the user can easily interpret it at any other time scale T .

In fact the Brownian motion W satisfies a much stronger self-similarity property, namely, the distributions of the processes $(W_{\lambda t}, t > 0)$ and $(\sqrt{\lambda}W_t, t > 0)$ coincide. This has obvious implications for the calculations of prices of path dependent options.

In the original SABR model a bivariate Brownian motion (W, Z) with correlation ρ is used to define the dynamics of the asset and of its volatility. Note that (W, Z) is self-similar in the following sense. The distributions of the processes $((W_{\lambda t}, Z_{\lambda t}), t > 0)$ and $((\lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}W_t, \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}Z_t), t > 0)$ coincide.

In our generalization of the SABR model we proposed to replace the Brownian motion Z with a fractional Brownian motion. Note that the covariance function of the Gaussian process $(Z_{\lambda t}, t > 0)$ satisfies

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(|\lambda s|^{2H} + |\lambda t|^{2H} - |\lambda t - \lambda s|^{2H} \right) = \lambda^{2H} \frac{1}{2} \left(|s|^{2H} + |t|^{2H} - |t - s|^{2H} \right)$$

and hence it coincides with the covariance function of the process $(\lambda^H Z_t, t > 0)$. This means that the fractional Brownian motion is self-similar with the Hurst exponent H . Obviously, for the classical Brownian motion $H = \frac{1}{2}$.

So far we have constructed two bivariate Gaussian processes, one based on the Molchan-Golosov formula, and the other on Mandelbrot-Van Ness formula. Both lead to a bivariate Gaussian process (W, Z) in which the marginals are self-similar with Hurst exponents $\frac{1}{2}$ and H , respectively. What about the bivariate process (W, Z) ?

In the next step we introduce the concept of multivariate fractional Brownian motion and of the multivariate self-similarity. In our setup we will only need these for bivariate processes.

We adapt the definitions from Amblard et al. (2011).

Definition 1 *A Multivariate fractional Brownian motion with parameter $H \in (0, 1)^p$ is a p -dimensional continuous process satisfying the following three properties*

- It is Gaussian,
- It is self-similar with vector parameter $H \in (0, 1)^p$,
- It has stationary increments.

Here, self-similarity is understood as the joint self-similarity. More precisely, we use the following definition.

Definition 2 *—A multivariate process $(X(t) = (X_1(t), \dots, X_p(t))), t \in R$ is self-similar if there exists a vector $H = (H_1, \dots, H_p) \in (0, 1)^p$ such that for any $\lambda > 0$ the distributions of processes*

$$((X_1(\lambda t), \dots, X_p(\lambda t))), t \in R$$

and

$$(\lambda^{H_1} X_1(t), \dots, \lambda^{H_p} X_p(t), t \in R)$$

coincide. Vector H is the self-similarity parameter.

5 Covariance

Assume that the process (W, Z) is a bivariate fractional Brownian motion with parameter $(\frac{1}{2}, H)$. What is the dependence structure between W and Z ?

It turns out that the answer can be easily deduced from the general results of Amblard et al. (2011), Coeurjolly et al. (2010) Lavancier et al. (2009). Indeed, they prove that there exist two constants $\delta \in [-1, 1]$ and $\eta \in R$ such that for $0 < s < t$ we have

$$EW_s Z_t = \frac{1}{2} \left((\delta + \eta) |s|^{H+\frac{1}{2}} + (\delta - \eta) |t|^{H+\frac{1}{2}} - (\delta - \eta) |t - s|^{H+\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

and for $0 < t < s$

$$EW_s Z_t = \frac{1}{2} \left((\delta + \eta) |s|^{H+\frac{1}{2}} + (\delta - \eta) |t|^{H+\frac{1}{2}} - (\delta + \eta) |t-s|^{H+\frac{1}{2}} \right),$$

where $\delta = EW_1 Z_1$. In our case, when W is a Brownian motion, the above formulae can be simplified even further. For $0 < t < s$ we deduce, because of martingale property of W with respect to filtration \mathcal{F} to which also Z is adapted and of bivariate self-similarity of (W, Z) , that

$$EW_s Z_t = EZ_t E(W_s | \mathcal{F}_t) = EZ_t W_t = Et^H Z_1 t^{\frac{1}{2}} W_1 = t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} EW_1 Z_1 = \delta t^{H+\frac{1}{2}}.$$

It follows from the previous general expressions that

$$\eta = -\delta,$$

and consequently the dependence structure of the bivariate fractional Brownian motion (W, Z) is given by

$$EW_s Z_t = \delta \begin{cases} t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} - (t-s)^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & , 0 < s < t \\ t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & , 0 < t < s \end{cases},$$

where

$$\delta = \frac{\rho}{c_1(H) \left(H + \frac{1}{2}\right)},$$

and

$$c_1(H) = \left(\int_0^\infty \left((1+u)^{H-\frac{1}{2}} - u^{H-\frac{1}{2}} \right)^2 du + \frac{1}{2H} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Remark 3 Note that when we use the Mandelbrot Van Ness formula to define the fractional Brownian motion Z , we define the bivariate Gaussian process (W, Z) which is a bivariate fractional Brownian motion with the vector parameter $(\frac{1}{2}, H)$.

Remark 4 One can also prove this directly, without making reference to the general results of Amblard et al. (2011). Indeed, we have

$$\begin{aligned} EW_{\lambda s} Z_{\lambda t} &= \delta \begin{cases} (\lambda t)^{H+\frac{1}{2}} - (\lambda t - \lambda s)^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & , 0 < s < t \\ (\lambda t)^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & , 0 < t < s \end{cases} \\ &= \lambda^{H+\frac{1}{2}} \delta \begin{cases} t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} - (t-s)^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & , 0 < s < t \\ t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} & , 0 < t < s \end{cases} = E\lambda^{\frac{1}{2}} W_s \lambda^H Z_t. \end{aligned}$$

and hence the distributions of the processes

$$((W_{\lambda t}, Z_{\lambda t}), t \in R)$$

and

$$\left(\lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}W_t, \lambda^H Z_t, t \in R\right)$$

coincide. This means that the process (W, Z) , where Z is given by the Mandelbrot Van Ness formula, is a bivariate fractional Brownian motion with the parameter $(\frac{1}{2}, H)$. One can consider the case when $t \in R$ or when $t > 0$.

6 Fractional SABR model

The fractional SABR model is defined by the following expressions

$$dX_t = X_t^\beta Y_t dW_t, X_0 = x, 0 \leq \beta \leq 1, \alpha \geq 0,$$

$$Y_t = \sigma \exp\left(\alpha Z_t - \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2 t^{2H}\right), 0 < H < 1,$$

where (W, Z) is a bivariate fractional Brownian motion with the vector parameter $(\frac{1}{2}, H)$. The above system can also be written as follows

$$dX_t = X_t^\beta dM_t, X_0 = x,$$

where

$$M_t = \int_0^t Y_s dW_s.$$

Clearly, the equation for X remains the same as in the CEV model but the stochastic driver changes from W to the martingale M . Obviously, the properties of the model will be determined by the properties of the martingale M . Here we are focusing on scaling.

In order to study scaling properties in our model we indicate the dependence of the volatility process Y and of the martingale M on the model parameters by introducing the following notation

$$Y_t^{\alpha, \sigma} = \sigma \exp\left(\alpha Z_t - \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2 t^{2H}\right)$$

and

$$M_t^{\alpha, \sigma} = \int_0^t Y_s^{\alpha, \sigma} dW_s.$$

Note that self-similarity of Z implies equality of distributions of the following processes

$$(Y_{\lambda t}^{\alpha, \sigma}, t > 0)$$

and

$$(Y_t^{\alpha \lambda^H, \sigma}, t > 0).$$

Indeed

$$Y_{\lambda t}^{\alpha, \sigma} = \sigma \exp\left(\alpha Z_{\lambda t} - \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2 (\lambda t)^{2H}\right)$$

$$\stackrel{\mathcal{D}}{=} \sigma \exp \left(\alpha \lambda^H Z_t - \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 \lambda^{2H} t^{2H} \right) = Y_t^{\alpha \lambda^H, \sigma},$$

where the second equality means equal distributions.

For the martingale M , thanks to the joint self-similarity of (W, Z) , we can deduce that the distributions of the processes

$$(M_{\lambda t}^{\alpha, \sigma}, t > 0)$$

and

$$\left(M_t^{\alpha \lambda^H, \sigma \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}}, t > 0 \right)$$

coincide. Indeed, we easily see that

$$M_{\lambda t}^{\alpha, \sigma} = \int_0^{\lambda t} Y_s^{\alpha, \sigma} dW_s = \int_0^t Y_{\lambda u}^{\alpha, \sigma} dW_{\lambda u}$$

$$\stackrel{\mathcal{D}}{=} \int_0^t \sigma \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left(\alpha \lambda^H Z_u - \frac{1}{2} \alpha^2 \lambda^{2H} u^{2H} \right) dW_u = \int_0^t Y_u^{\alpha \lambda^H, \sigma \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}} dW_u = M_t^{\alpha \lambda^H, \sigma \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}},$$

where the third equality means equal distributions.

There are five parameters in our model, namely $\sigma, \alpha, \beta, \rho$ and H . The first two, σ and α represent volatility. From the above analysis we see that they scale differently. The volatility σ scales by $\lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and the volatility of volatility α scales by λ^H . Parameters β and ρ determine shape of the smile and many mathematical properties of the model. The H parameter captures the ATM volatility skew.

In our next result we exploit the scaling. For this we introduce notation which indicates the dependence of the process X on the parameters α and σ , namely, $X^{\alpha, \sigma}$. It is easy to prove the following

Proposition 5 *Under the appropriate measurability and integrability conditions on the function G we have*

$$EG(X_T^{\alpha, \sigma}) = EG\left(X_1^{\alpha T^H, \sigma T^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right).$$

Proof. Recall that the equation for X written in terms of the martingale M has a unique strong solution. Therefore the solution can be written as follows

$$X_T^{\alpha, \sigma} = F(M_t^{\alpha, \sigma}; 0 \leq t \leq T)$$

for a certain functional F of path of $M^{\alpha, \sigma}$. Now using the bivariate self-similarity we get

$$\begin{aligned} EG(X_T^{\alpha, \sigma}) &= EG(F(M_t^{\alpha, \sigma}; 0 \leq t \leq T)) \\ &= EG\left(F\left(M_t^{\alpha T^H, \sigma T^{\frac{1}{2}}}; 0 \leq t \leq 1\right)\right) = EG\left(X_1^{\alpha T^H, \sigma T^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

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7 At-the-money volatility skew

We are now going to estimate the at-the-money volatility skew implied by the fractional SABR model. Recall that, in the classical SABR model with $H = \frac{1}{2}$, when strike K is not too far from the forward x the implied volatility can be approximated by (Hagan et al. (2002))

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{BS}(k, 1) &= \sigma x^{\beta-1} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta - \rho\delta) k \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{12} \left((1 - \beta)^2 + (2 - 3\rho^2) \delta^2 \right) k^2 + \dots \right), \end{aligned}$$

where for strike K and forward x

$$k = \log \frac{x}{K}$$

represents log-moneyness and

$$\delta = \frac{\alpha}{\sigma} x^{\beta-1}.$$

Therefore

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, 1) = \sigma x^{\beta-1} \left(\frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta - \rho\delta) + \frac{1}{6} \left((1 - \beta)^2 + (2 - 3\rho^2) \delta^2 \right) k + \dots \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, 1) |_{k=0} &= \sigma x^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta - \rho\delta) \\ &= Y_0 X_0^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta - \rho) \frac{\alpha}{\sigma} X_0^{\beta-1}. \end{aligned}$$

For time to expiration τ using scaling we get

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, \tau) |_{k=0} = Y_0 X_0^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta) - \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{\alpha \tau^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\sigma \tau^{\frac{1}{2}}} X_0^{\beta-1} = \frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, 1)$$

and hence the at-the-money volatility skew is flat in time to expiration.

In the fractional SABR, however, the volatility parameters α and σ scale differently in time to expiration. Using scaling of fractional SABR in

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, 1) |_{k=0}$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial k} \sigma_{BS}(k, \tau) |_{k=0} &= Y_0 X_0^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta) - \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{\alpha \tau^H}{\sigma \tau^{\frac{1}{2}}} X_0^{\beta-1} \\ &= Y_0 X_0^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta) - \frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{\alpha}{\sigma} X_0^{\beta-1} \tau^{H-\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\sigma_{BS}(k, 1)$ corresponds to the implied volatility of the classical SABR for log-moneyness k and time to expiration 1 and not that of the fractional SABR. By applying scaling to this volatility we effectively assume that

$$\sigma_{BS}(k, 1) = \sigma_{BS}^H(k, 1),$$

where $\sigma_{BS}^H(k, 1)$ denotes the implied volatility of the fractional SABR with Hurst exponent H and hence we assume that the at-the-money volatility skew for time to expiration 1 is flat in the Hurst exponent H . We are happy to make this assumption because our intention here is to explain the role of scaling and show consistency with known results. Alternatively, we could approximate $\frac{\partial}{\partial k}\sigma_{BS}(k, \tau)|_{k=0}$ by a linear function of $\frac{\alpha}{\sigma}$ which leads to the same conclusion.

Recall that

$$dX_t = X_t^\beta Y_t dW_t = X_t X_t^{\beta-1} Y_t dW_t$$

and hence $Y_0 X_0^{\beta-1}$, which approximates $X_t^{\beta-1} Y_t$ in the above expression, should be interpreted as an approximation to the short time lognormal volatility.

When $\beta \rightarrow 1$ we get

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial k}\sigma_{BS}(k, \tau)|_{k=0} = -\frac{1}{2}\rho\sigma\tau^{H-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

We assume negative correlation $\rho < 0$.

For $\beta < 1$ we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial k}\sigma_{BS}(k, \tau)|_{k=0} = Y_0 X_0^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2}(1-\beta) - \frac{1}{2}\rho\frac{\alpha}{\sigma} X_0^{\beta-1} \tau^{H-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

For short time to expiration we recover the result of Fukasawa (2017). Moreover, scaling argument proves the power law behavior of the at-the-money volatility skew for any time to expiration.

This property is the main difference between the classical SABR with $H = \frac{1}{2}$, where the skew is flat, and the fractional SABR with $H < \frac{1}{2}$, where the skew obeys the power law with the negative exponent $H - \frac{1}{2}$.

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